

ASTROLOGICAL REASONS FOR REMARRIAGE IN FEMALE'S HOROSCOPES

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Abstract:

Astrological reason for remarriage in an individual horoscope analysis is done here with examples and remedies are given

Key Words: Divorce, Spouse Death, Planetary Position, Remarriage, Reason, Remedy

Introduction:

Seventh bhava is very important to express the wedding life is happy or unhappy. It shows the status and the character of the spouse. It shows above the martial status is single, married or divorce. Every man expects a perfect wife. Every woman expects a perfect husband. Marriage makes a bond between a man and the woman.

Marriage Timings:

Rahu plays a vital role in marriage. Rahu and Kethu are karmic planets. Most of the marriages happened on Rahu's dasha or bhukthi or anthram.

Some other times for Marriage:

- Dasa, bukthi periods of the planets which stays in 2, 7 or 11th bhavas.
- Dasa, bukti periods of the Lords of 2, 7 or 11th bhavas.
- Current Dasa lord connect with navamsa lagna lord in transit period.
- Current Dasa lord connects with navamsa seventh lord in transit period should given remarriage for women.

Kuja Dosha:

Mars is located in the houses 2 or 4 or 7 or 8 or 12 from Lagna is called kuja dosha. It affects the intercourse desire. So, the best astrologer should match the kuja dosha horoscope with kuja dosha.

Reason for Divorce:

- The conjunction of mars and Jupiter in 2 or 4 or 7 or 8 or 12 from Lagna or Rasi.
- The aspect of Jupiter to Mars.
- The aspect of Mars to Jupiter.
- Seventh lord occupies fifth bhava.
- Jupiter, Mars and Venus located each other kendra or triangle.
- Jupiter, Mars and Venus joined each other with 8.30 degree should given divorce.

Which Lady Will do Remarriage:

- Seventh lord is with Rahu.
- Moon in 4th bhava and Rahu in 12th bhava with malefic planets.
- 4th bhava is affected by Mars, Saturn, Rahu or kethu.
- Mars, Saturn, Rahu or kethu occupies in 7th bhava.

Which Man Will do Remarriage:

- Mars, Saturn, Rahu or kethu occupies second or seventh bhava.
- Venus in eleventh house or connect with eleventh house lord.
- Retrograde planet in eleventh house or eleventh lord is in retro grade.
- Seventh lord got vargothama.
- Seventh or twelfth lord, occupies the second house.
- Seventh house lord connects with fifth house lord.
- Seventh house lord stands in movable signs Aries, Cancer, Libra and Capricorn should given remarriage for man.

Example 1:

Name	:	S. Meena
Date of Birth	:	04.06.1979
Time of birth	:	06.13 pm
Place of birth	:	Tuticorin
Janma Lagna	:	Scorpio

Janma Rasi : Virgo
 Janma Star : Uthiram 4th Padam
 Saturn dasa balance : 1 year 3 Months 4 Days

	Venus Mars	Mercury Sun	
Kethu	Rasi		Jupiter
			Rahu saturn
	Asc	Manthi	Moon

Kethu Moon			Sun
	Navamsa		Saturn Mercury
Venus	Asc	Jupiter Mars Manthi	Rahu

Planet	Degree	Star	Padam	Rasi	Navamsa
Lagna	225.47	Anuradha	4	Scorpio	Scorpio
Sun	049.44	Rohini	3	Taurus	Gemini
Moon	157.11	Uthiram	4	Virgo	Pisces
Mars	020.48	Bharani	3	Aries	Libra
Mercury	056.33	Mirugasira	1	Taurus	Leo
Jupiter	102.12	Pusam	3	Cancer	Libra
Venus	027.39	Karithika	1	Aries	Sagittarius
Saturn	134.06	Puram	1	Leo	Leo
Rahu	139.28	Puram	2	Leo	Virgo
Kethu	319.28	Sathayam	4	Aquaris	Pisces
Manti	182.14	Chithra	3	Libra	Libra

Sun dasa till	1 year	2 Months	4 Days
Moon dasa till	11 years	3 Months	4 Days
Mars dasa till	18 years	3 Months	4 Days
Rahu dasa till	36 years	3 Months	4 Days
Guru dasa till	52 years	3 Months	4 Days

How Our Rules Give Result in this Horoscope?

Two rules are applicable out of ten

1. Rule Number 3: (Reason for divorce)

The aspect of Mars to; Jupiter should given divorce. This rule becomes true in this horoscope.

2. Rule Number 3: (Which lady will do re marriage)

Fourth bhava is affected by Mars, saturn, Ragu or kethu.

In this horoscope Kethu occupies the fourth house and also seen by the house lord saturn. It is very very dangerous one. Now she got divorce and lives with her two children in her father's shadow.

3. Example 2:

Name : Linga lakshmi
 Date of Birth : 17.09.1978
 Time of birth : 10.05 am
 Place of birth : Chennai
 Janma Lagna : Libra
 Janma Rasi : Pisces
 Janma Star : Uthira bhadrapada
 Saturn dasa balance : 17 years 4 Months 24 Days

Moon Kethu	7	8	9
Manthi	Rasi		Jupiter
4			Saturn Mercury
3	2	Mars Venus Asc	Sun Rahu

10	11	12	Asc
Venus	Navamsa		Kethu Saturn
Rahu Sun			Moon
7	Mars	Manthi	Jupiter Mercury

Planet	Degree	Star	Padam	Rasi	Navamsa
Lagna	209.30	Visaga	3	Libra	Gemini
Sun	150.18	Uthiram	2	Viro	Capricorn
Moon	334.27	Uthiratathi	1	Pisces	Leo
Mars	184.36	Chitra	4	Libra	Scorpio
Mercury	138.43	Pooram	2	Leo	Virgo
Jupiter	098.34	Poosam	2	Cancer	Virgo
Venus	194.47	Swathi	3	Libra	Aquaris
Saturn	133.00	Magam	4	Leo	Cancer
Rahu	153.16	Uthiram	2	Virgo	Capricorn
Kethu	333.16	Pooratathi	4	Pisces	Cancer
Manti	302.10	Danista	3	Aquaris	Libra

Sun dasa till age	17 years	4 Months	24 Days
Mercury dasa till age	34 years	4 Months	24 Days
Kethu dasa till age	41 years	4 Months	24 Days
Moon dassa own bukthi	44 years	8 Months	24 Days

How Our Rules Apply in this Horoscope?

Two rules are applicable out of ten

1. Rule Number 5: (Reason for Divorce)

Jupiter, Mars and Venus located each other in kendra or triangle.

In this horoscope Venus and Mars are in Libra. From Libra the tenth kendra house Cancer, there Jupiter stands. So, the above rule brought her divorce.

2. Rule Number 3: (Which Lady Will do Remarriage)

Fourth bhava is affected by Mars Saturn, Rahu or Kethu. In this horoscope fourth house was aspected by Mars by its 4th aspect. And also the fourth bhava lord is located at eighth house from Capricorn, This confirm the dangerous result.

Divine Remedy:

Woman who has the above combinations the rules given by me should worship Lord Magudeeswara at Kodumudi. First of all they select the best day, from new moon 23.11.2022 to full moon 08.12.2022 The day should have nethram (eyes) and jeevan (soul). It is must the parihar day must have dhara balam (strength of star). From One's Janma star 2, 6, 15, 20, 24 stars are very best to do parihar. One should select any one day from the above five.

It gives quick result.

Example to Choose the Particular Day to Do Parihar:

i.e Linga Lakshmi's

Second star is Revathi 2.12.2022 Saturday

Sixth star is Rohini 7.12.2022 Wednesday

Fifteenth star is Hastham not come in Suklabakcha Thi Thi

Twentieth star is Jyeshtha 25 11.22 Friday

Twenty fourth star is Sravanam 28.11.22 Monday

There are Five Options for Us:

We can reject Revathi star 02.12.2022 because of it falls on Saturday. We also reject the fifteenth star Hastham because it not comes under the period of sukla pakcham. The twentieth star Jyeshtha star 25.11.2022 comes under marana yoga so, we reject this. Similarly the twenty fourth star Sravanam star 28.11.2022 also comes under marana yoga. So, the one and the only, option is the sixth star sathaga tharai Rohini 07.12.2022 Wednesday, comes with Amritha yoga. It has nethram 2, jeevan 1. It gives good result for parihar. Thus method we should follow to take the best day for parihar. Then we choose the best lagna which is aspected by Jupiter. It should not 6, 8, 12th lagna from the pariharam doers Janma lagna.

Remedial Pooja done by the Priest:

The prist makes 9 navagraha kalasa (metal pot) and 2 family diety kalasa. He does Ganapathi homam, and navagraha homam. After that the pariharam doing man tie thirumangalayam to the plantain tree / woman tie thirumangalayam to the Kalasa. Then he/she takes bath in Cauvery River After that worship lord Magudeeswara and do archana and happily return to home. Surely their dosa will vanish. I have sent my, so many clients to Mr. Ramesh, the priest at Kodumudi His mobile number is 7502207409. He does the parihar pooja very well and removes the remarriage dosha at nominal cost.

Conclusion:

Change the fate through the moon is a proverb. So, we give more importance to select the parihar day. With the help of God we can easily solve our problems through astrology.

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